

MentorStudio: Amplifying diverse voices through rapid, self-authorable virtual mentors

Benjamin D. Nye¹[0000-0002-5902-9196], Yuko Okado²[0000-0002-5077-4245], Aaron Shiel¹, Kayla Carr¹, Milton Rosenberg¹, Enora Rice¹, Luke Ostrander¹, Megan Ju¹, Cassandra Gutierrez¹, Dilan R. Ramirez¹, Daniel Auerbach¹, Angelica Aguirre², and William Swartout¹[0000-0002-7436-6940]

¹ University of Southern California Institute for Creative Technologies, Playa Vista, CA 90094, USA nye@ict.usc.edu,

² California State University, Fullerton, Fullerton CA 92831, USA yokado@fullerton.edu

Abstract. Mentoring promotes underserved students’ STEM persistence but it is difficult to scale up. Virtual agents can amplify mentors’ experiences to larger audiences, which is particularly important for mentors from under-represented backgrounds and for underserved students with less access to mentors. This paper introduces MentorStudio, an online platform that allows real-life mentors to self-record and publish video-based conversational virtual agents. MentorStudio’s goals are to increase speed, scheduling flexibility, and autonomy in creating intelligent virtual mentors. MentorStudio platform components are introduced, along with initial feedback regarding usability and acceptance collected from 20 STEM mentors who recorded virtual mentors. Overall, the MentorStudio platform has good ease-of-use and acceptance among mentors and offers a platform capable of recording large number of mentors to expand their reach to an unlimited number of students.

Keywords: Virtual Agents · Mentoring · Authoring Tools · STEM

1 Introduction

Virtual mentoring offers an important option for increasing access of under-represented minority (URM³) students to mentors with similar backgrounds and/or in careers where they would otherwise lack access to mentors in their social networks [8]. However, typical virtual mentoring programs simply transfer mentoring to online modality (e.g., teleconferencing) [10] and face problems with scaling. Virtual agent mentors have the potential to scale up access to mentors, which could incrementally build resources such as a “virtual career fair” or virtual mentor agents who specialize in certain skills or topics. In this work, we

³ URM as defined by National Science Foundation in this research, though virtual mentors are likely to be relevant to broader definitions.

focus on conversational agents based on recorded human videos, which can compellingly convey personal experiences [17] with digital narratives that increase engagement and learning [7].

In earlier research on such virtual mentor agents, a high school STEM outreach project (MentorPal) demonstrated that it was feasible to video-record real-life mentors answering questions often asked by mentees and use these to generate conversational virtual agent-mentors [12,13]. Students could pick from suggested questions or type/speak their own questions, where natural language understanding would respond with the mentor’s best-match answer. However, students requested more mentors, representing more careers and more diverse identities (particularly gender). To address this need, we developed MentorStudio, a web-based platform that (1) allows mentors to self-record, edit, and publish their own virtual mentors, with the goal of allowing mentors to (2) conduct outreach via the CareerFair.ai portal, a virtual career fair where students can explore and learn about diverse mentors’ career paths through virtual mentor conversations. A recent study on CareerFair.ai at a large United States Hispanic-Serving Institution (HSI) university showed high user acceptance, positive pre-post results, and particularly strong outcomes for URM students [14]. In this companion paper, we describe progress on technologies to scale up this type of mentoring.

2 Background and Rationale

MentorPal, the virtual agent technology for video-based agent-mentors, was most directly inspired by the New Dimensions in Testimony project, which enabled museum visitors to converse with hologram recordings of Holocaust survivors to learn about their personal experiences, producing strong engagement in survivors’ stories and lives [18]. Compared to other approaches in intelligent mentoring, such as embodied pedagogical agents or text chat [5,6], we posit that career narratives are inherently personal, developmental, and intersectional. As such, video-based mentors offer greater authenticity versus a generated agent.

Virtual mentors offer three mechanisms to support students who are under-represented in a career field: a) greater access to mentors from fields not well-connected through their social networks (particular first-generation college students), b) sharing strategies and lessons-learned from mentors with similar identities or life experiences, and c) as an introduction or for building self-confidence contact a real-life mentor (e.g., “contact by email” functionality). These are important because the space of career experiences is vast, with thousands of careers even just in STEM, and with life experiences covering not just traditional demographics (e.g., race, gender, age, socio-economic status) but also broader issues such as disabilities, neurodiversity, religion, geographic region, and “deep similarities” in beliefs [2]. By selecting mentors to support different populations of students, virtual mentors can expand different both types of support and research can investigate mentor-student interactions in this context.

However, even from the earliest MentorPal outreach with high-school students [13], virtual mentor generation was a bottleneck for representing different

experiences. Despite a focus on rapid mentor creation, this first cohort of 5 mentors took approximately 145 person-hours by the last mentor, even with only one interviewer assisting. While MentorPal was substantially faster than traditional approaches to make a comparable mentor, it relied on an offline pipeline with manual steps such as confirming start/stop times for answers and required computer science or audio-visual editing expertise was required for some steps.

Table 1 shows estimated time required to build a mentor using the original MentorPal authoring pipeline and expected time savings by potential automation, considering time spent by both the mentor and research team. Anticipated time-savings were from automating interviews (+20h), generating mentor-specific questions (+10h), video post-production (+14h), and cleaning transcripts (+21h). In addition to the time requirements, scheduling flexibility was a distinct barrier: most mentors required scheduled recording sessions to configure software and pose questions. This paper reflects on how MentorStudio addressed these barriers versus areas where researchers and coordinators remain essential.

Development Step	Estimated Hours (Final Mentor)	Projected Hours (With Automation)
Create questions specific to a career or mentor	15	5
Mentor answering 300+ questions on video	18	18
Post-production (sound, lighting, clip start/end)	16	2
Clean up automated transcripts	36	15
Update content based on real student questions	25	15
Administrative effort (schedule & setup sessions)	15	15
Total (Self-Recorded Mentor)	125	70
Total (One Interviewer +20h)	145	90
Total (Two Interviewers + 40h)	165	110

Table 1. Original MentorPal (2018) Estimates

3 MentorStudio Design Approach

MentorStudio addressed three goals related to diversity, equity, and inclusion in developing intelligent virtual mentors: (1) By reducing barriers to recording, a broader set of mentor careers and backgrounds can be represented, to increase engagement and knowledge of STEM careers among URM students [14]; (2) Reducing time commitments for mentors who volunteer to record; and (3) Adding administrative tools for organizations to manage their own mentors, reducing or removing our role as “middlemen,” to give mentors and outreach organizations greater autonomy in building and sharing their virtual mentors. Capabilities related to the student-facing side of the system are noted elsewhere [14].

Reflecting on Table 1, the research team played the following roles: Administrative Coordinator, Setup Guide, Interviewer, Basic Videographer, and Content Editor. Of these, content editing was by far the least efficient process: correcting automated transcription errors for subtitles was the most time-consuming task. The following sections describe MentorStudio features designed to automate parts of each role, as well as parts that could not be automated.

3.1 Mentor Setup Guide and Session Scheduling

MentorStudio’s first design priority was that a new mentor could build an initial interactive mentor in their first 15 minutes. This is because “preview” (e.g., quickly seeing what a student will see) is a key feature for content authors [11,15]. New users log in using OAuth (e.g., Google) and are guided through four activities: Setup Wizard, Upload Profile Image, Record 5 Questions, Build Mentor, and Preview Mentor. The Setup Wizard starts by asking for: i) a brief bio (name, profession), ii) their mentor display (e.g., standard vs. virtual background vs. chat only), iii) privacy settings, iv) a 1-2 sentence mentoring goal, and v) experiences and identity tags that they can select or write-in (e.g., gender, first-generation college). This data helps students browse or search for relevant mentors. Mentors then select “Subjects” that organize categories of questions to record. For this project, STEM Careers is the main subject, containing 258 questions derived from prior MentorPal research and needs analysis with over 1000 HSI students. Other subjects include special topics, such as Computer Science.

Next, mentors record three essential videos for their mentor: Idle, Introduction, and Off-Topic. The Idle video involves sitting in position of “attentive and waiting for the student’s question” for up to 60 seconds. This video is looped when the agent is visible but not speaking to increase realism. When recording, mentors see their live video feed, and a silhouette is provided to help them stay in a consistent position. The Introduction video plays when a mentor greets a student, to give their name, career, and conversational “hooks” for things students may want to ask about. Finally, the Off-Topic video responds to questions where the agent’s classifier model cannot find a confident answer.

Following the initial Setup, the My Mentor page (Fig. 1) shows their recording status. On their first visit to My Mentor, a sequence of tooltips explain each element (e.g., Build, Recommended Next Step). If mentors have not completed Setup, My Mentor suggests returning to the next incomplete step. After 5 questions (including the Introduction) are recorded, the Build button will train their classifier (typically 5-60 seconds). Mentors then Preview their virtual mentor to ask it questions. Based on over 2 years of mentor recording and usability surveys, the setup process was iteratively tuned, expanded (e.g., tooltips), and simplified.

On the converse, Administrative Coordinator responsibilities (e.g., scheduling recording sessions) were not automated. Given the importance of acknowledging the donation of mentors’ time, all outreach was done through direct correspondence from the research team. While MentorStudio made it possible for some mentors to comfortably record all questions after a single introductory session, the typical schedule included a 1h introductory session and two brief (20-30min) check-ins with feedback on videos recorded so far. These video-conferences typically focused on consistent visual appearance (e.g., new recordings do not match the setup Idle), considering the audience (e.g., explaining acronyms), answering a mentor’s questions about question intent (e.g., “What do people usually cover in this answer?”), and troubleshooting / bug reports. A meeting after finishing was also common, to thank the mentor and allow any final feedback.

Fig. 1. MyMentor Authoring Home Page

3.2 Mentor “Interviewer” Features

Compared to a human video interviewer, MentorStudio performs a limited set of tasks: it organizes questions, tracks progress in covering the topics, records the responses, shows the results to help check for issues, and suggests limited follow-up questions. However, this is offset by running tasks very quickly for immediate feedback and rapid iteration. As shown in Fig. 1, mentors see questions organized into categories and can record either a single question or step through a whole set of questions. Recorded questions are uploaded to cloud services in parallel, which generate transcriptions, mobile vs. desktop versions, and add them to the classifier training data set. Compared to early versions of MentorPal, modern transcription API’s are accurate enough to save many hours of correction.

A queue similar to a web-browser “downloads” shows the completion progress. As a result, mentors can continuously record answers as earlier uploads process. They can also preview their recorded video before uploading, so they can optimize takes to best present their personal narratives and information. By comparison, in original MentorPal interviews, mentors would often ask permission or hesitate to re-record a question, and re-recording a question later was challenging. Likewise, MentorStudio’s Build (training the classifier) and Preview can be done in 1-2 minutes rather than multiple weeks.

To help mentors follow best practices (Record→Build→Preview), MentorStudio provides a next-step recommender (the “Go” button in the upper-right *Improve Your Mentor* section). A simple production rule system recommends steps based on setup completion, coverage of the mentor (amount of questions recorded), and quality improvement (unaddressed user feedback). Qualitative differences in question coverage (called Phases, see: “Interactive” in Fig. 1) change how active production rules are weighted. For example, new mentors are primarily directed

to record more pre-existing subject questions, while mentors with many questions should check for new questions that students asked but the mentor could not answer (i.e., the User Feedback - Trending questions area). This functionality helps ensure mentors always have a reasonable action to improve their mentor.

3.3 Mentor Video Recording and Processing

The interface for recording each video is shown in Fig. 2. The question to record is shown under a video player. If a video is already recorded, the transcript will be shown below and the video can be replayed. If mentors opt to record or re-record, a video recorder gives a countdown with a silhouette to help the mentor start in the right position. Recording a question finishes when the mentor hits their spacebar or clicks a button. The spacebar shortcut was added based on mentor feedback, to help avoid looking away while ending the video. Videos are limited to a maximum length (5 minutes), with suggested duration of 30s to 2.5m. As part of the human coaching, mentors are also instructed that students respond best to engaging narratives and that a long response is still excellent so long as it highlights key takeaways. Further research is warranted on kinds of coaching that result in videos with the highest student engagement and learning.

Fig. 2. Video Recording User Interface

Finally, several mentors requested the option for a virtual background, mainly to facilitate maintaining a consistent background or to increase privacy. We found that virtual backgrounds for mentors are more complex than video-conference backgrounds for two reasons. First, mentors must view their recording in real-time (no lag) by segmenting their video in-browser even on standard laptops. This was achieved by combining Google’s Selfie Segmentation library [3], which processed the raw video feed in-browser for a Video.js web player. Second, mentors need to change their background without re-processing every recorded video.

This was accomplished by segmenting the person from the video and replacing the remainder with a transparent alpha channel. On playback, the video player displays an image with the same dimensions in the background, allowing mentors to upload a new background image anytime. This capability remains in a beta stage but appears to be viable based on trial usage by a few mentors.

3.4 Personalized Questions: Trending and Follow-Up Questions

MentorStudio implements two capabilities to help mentors address unanticipated student questions: Trending Questions and Follow-Up Question Generation. Trending questions are inferred from student questions actually posed to the mentor that may have been answered poorly (i.e., marked as off-topic/no answer, low confidence in answer, or student used “thumbs down” on the answer). Recently-asked problematic questions (approx. 200) are grouped based on similarity of sentence embeddings [16] and presented in a “Trending Questions” panel sorted to show the most common issues. Mentors may choose to select an existing question that answers the users’ question (label), queue the question on My Mentor to record later (record), or dismiss the question (won’t answer/off topic).

However, when human interviewers are present, they can suggest follow-up questions even before students ask them. To address this issue, when a mentor finishes recording a set of questions, follow-up questions are generated based on named entity recognition and dependency parsing for people, places, organizations, job titles, and family members (SpaCy; [4]). Each entity is given a ranking score, based on context cues from dependency parsing for their associated verb and sentence subject [9]. Ranking scores are higher when the verb is relevant to the mentor’s set of answers (cosine similarity of sentence embeddings) and when the mentor is the subject (“I”). To eliminate redundant questions, questions are filtered using paraphrase mining [16] against the mentor’s recorded and subject questions. While not perfect, this approach generates simple but reasonable follow-ups (e.g., “Can you tell me about McDonald’s?” is suggested for a mentor who worked at McDonald’s, but not a mentor who only mentioned it.)

4 User Acceptance: Survey of Mentors

Each mentor completed a self-report Qualtrics survey providing feedback regarding usability and acceptance of the MentorStudio platform ($N=20$). On average, mentors reported 17.53 hours of use ($SD=9.60$, Range=8-35 after removing two outliers, one on each end of the distribution). They rated 13 items on ease of use, acceptance, and intent to use based on the Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology (UTAUT; [19]), from 1 (*completely disagree*) to 6 (*completely agree*). Mentors showed high acceptance of MentorStudio (average rating $M=5.02$, $SD=0.79$). Main themes are summarized in Table 2, where the highest-rated was “Using MentorStudio is a good idea” ($M=5.60$, $SD=0.60$) and lowest-rated was “Using MentorStudio increases my productivity” ($M=4.05$,

$SD=1.47$). Using the same rating scale, mentors also rated six separate features of MentorStudio, using three items (“clear and easy to understand”; “good idea”; “enables me to accomplish tasks more quickly”). The highest-rated feature was the Recording page ($M=5.18$, $SD=0.95$), followed by My Mentor page question list, Mentor Status display, Select Subjects page, Build and Preview Mentor feature, and Idle video set-up ($M=4.77$, $SD=0.93$). Mentors also provided write-in responses asking about bugs, confusing behavior, and features. Bugs were reported by 14 write-in responses (70%), with 6 mentioning problems with video upload and 4 indicating that any initial bugs were resolved. Only 6 mentors (30%) indicated finding an aspect of the platform confusing, with half of those responses indicating that those were temporary (e.g., “At first I was not sure of a few things but as I gained familiarity it became easier.”) and the other half indicating specific areas of initial confusion (e.g., adding and recording follow-up questions). A total of 13 (65%) mentors suggested desired features, with virtual background, navigation improvements, assistance with video positioning, and video editing features suggested by two mentors each. Other features (e.g., a larger stop recording button) were suggested by only one mentor each.

<i>Component</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>
Good Idea	5.60	0.60
Ease of Use	5.30	0.64
Expected Usefulness	4.85	1.09
Job Relevance	4.20	1.42
Like	5.08	1.14
Low Barrier	5.08	0.88
Use Again	5.50	0.83
Recommend	5.15	1.27

Table 2. Mentor UTAUT Ratings

5 Implications and Future Directions

Research on MentorStudio removed significant barriers to creating virtual mentors, both for individual mentors and for outreach organizations that might want to record or share mentors. Mentor ratings for usability and acceptance of the system were consistently high, and multiple features were implemented based on mentor feedback (e.g., virtual backgrounds, easier stop to recording). The barriers that were most effectively removed were for self-paced recording, content cleanup (improving transcript quality, re-recording videos which had problems), and audio-visual processing (e.g., segmenting or converting videos, helping mentors start in a consistent position). The roles where researchers remain the most involved are administrative coordination (mentor recruitment and first-time use meetings), developing new content areas and templates (e.g., question sets), and improving the quality of mentor’s answers (e.g., labeling better questions in user feedback, suggesting follow-up questions to be recorded). Thus, the system fills the most basic interviewer role, enhanced by human coordinators (e.g., providing better context on the reasons for the questions, common ways people answer, and superior follow-up questions). With that said, advances in generative AI may eventually create effective assistants in these areas.

Recruiting diverse mentors from underserved or URM backgrounds remains a challenge. Even with an efficient recording process, only a subset of mentors have time for approximately 12h of recordings needed to have a conversational mentor. As a result, while mentors recorded to date are more diverse than in STEM fields in general, reaching or exceeding the diversity of a broad student population remains a challenge. However, this may not stall the overall goals for increasing equity: HSI college students indicated that while mentors' careers and gender representation were important for mentor selection, their racial/ethnic background was surprisingly not a significant factor [14]. This implies that helping under-represented students access virtual mentors in their preferred careers and genders may be the top priority, though it might also indicate the need to consider deeper-level similarity (e.g., attitudes, motivations) rather than shallower demographic identities [1]. Thus, despite this challenge, the current MentorStudio model still shows promise for helping underserved or URM students access mentoring on-demand and in fields which are not represented in their social networks.

Acknowledgments. This material is based upon work supported by the National Defense Education Program (NDEP) for Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics (STEM) Education, Outreach, and Workforce Initiative Programs under Grant No. HQ0034-20-S-FO01. The views expressed in this publication do not necessarily reflect the official policies of the Department of Defense nor does mention of trade names, commercial practices, or organizations imply endorsement by the U.S. Government. We thank the CareerFair.ai project mentors, research assistants, and study participants.

References

1. Blake-Beard, S., Bayne, M.L., Crosby, F.J., Muller, C.B.: Matching by race and gender in mentoring relationships: Keeping our eyes on the prize. *Journal of Social Issues* **67**(3), 622–643 (2011). <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1540-4560.2011.01717.x>
2. Eby, L.T.d.T., Allen, T.D., Hoffman, B.J., Baranik, L.E., Sauer, J.B., Baldwin, S., Morrison, M.A., Kinkade, K.M., Maher, C.P., Curtis, S.: An interdisciplinary meta-analysis of the potential antecedents, correlates, and consequences of protégé perceptions of mentoring. *Psychological bulletin* **139**(2), 441 (2013)
3. Google: Mediapipe (2022), <https://github.com/google/mediapipe>
4. Honnibal, M., Montani, L.: spaCy 2: Natural language understanding with Bloom embeddings, convolutional neural networks and incremental parsing (2017)
5. Huff, E.W., Mack, N.A., Cummings, R., Womack, K., Gosha, K., Gilbert, J.E.: Evaluating the usability of pervasive conversational user interfaces for virtual mentoring. In: *Learning and Collaboration Technologies. Ubiquitous and Virtual Environments for Learning and Collaboration: 6th International Conference, LCT 2019, Held as Part of the 21st HCI International Conference, HCII 2019, Orlando, FL, USA, July 26–31, 2019, Proceedings, Part II* 21. pp. 80–98. Springer (2019)
6. Klamma, R., de Lange, P., Neumann, A.T., Hensen, B., Kravcik, M., Wang, X., Kuzilek, J.: Scaling mentoring support with distributed artificial intelligence. In:

- Intelligent Tutoring Systems: 16th International Conference, ITS 2020, Athens, Greece, June 8–12, 2020, Proceedings. pp. 38–44. Springer (2020)
7. McQuiggan, S.W., Rowe, J.P., Lee, S., Lester, J.C.: Story-based learning: The impact of narrative on learning experiences and outcomes. In: Intelligent Tutoring Systems. pp. 530–539. Springer Berlin Heidelberg (2008)
 8. McReynolds, M.R., Termini, C.M., Hinton Jr, A.O., Taylor, B.L., Vue, Z., Huang, S.C., Roby, R.S., Shuler, H., Carter, C.S.: The art of virtual mentoring in the twenty-first century for stem majors and beyond. *Nature Biotechnology* **38**(12), 1477–1482 (2020)
 9. Nasar, Z., Jaffry, S.W., Malik, M.K.: Named entity recognition and relation extraction: State-of-the-art. *ACM Computing Surveys (CSUR)* **54**(1), 1–39 (2021)
 10. Neely, A.R., Cotton, J., Neely, A.D.: E-mentoring: A model and review of the literature. *AIS Transactions on Human-Computer Interaction* **9**(3), 220–242 (2017)
 11. Nye, B., Jain, A., Ramirez, D., Core, M., Swartout, W.: Designing a rapid adaptive content registry (RACR) for adaptive learning. In: Interservice/Industry Simulation, Training and Education Conference (2022)
 12. Nye, B., Swartout, W., Campbell, J., Krishnamachari, M., Kaimakis, N., Davis, D.: Mentorpai: Interactive virtual mentors based on real-life stem professionals. In: Interservice/Industry Simulation, Training and Education Conference (2017)
 13. Nye, B.D., Davis, D.M., Rizvi, S.Z., Carr, K., Swartout, W., Thacker, R., Shaw, K.: Feasibility and usability of mentorpai, a framework for rapid development of virtual mentors. *Journal of Research on Technology in Education* **53**(1), 1–23 (2020)
 14. Okado, Y., Nye, B.D., Aguirre, A., Swartout, W.: Can virtual agents scale up mentoring?: Insights from college students’ experiences using the careerfair.ai platform at an american hispanic-serving institution. *Artificial Intelligence in Education Conference* (2023)
 15. Reddig, D., Karreman, J., van der Geest, T.: Watch out for the preview: The effects of a preview on the usability of a content management system and on the users’ confidence level. In: 2008 IEEE International Professional Communication Conference. pp. 1–7 (2008). <https://doi.org/10.1109/IPCC.2008.4610232>
 16. Reimers, N., Gurevych, I.: Sentence-bert: Sentence embeddings using siamese bert-networks. In: 9th EMNLP-IJCNLP Conference. pp. 3982–3992 (2019)
 17. Swartout, W., Artstein, R., Forbell, E., Foutz, S., Lane, H.C., Lange, B., Morie, J., Noren, D., Rizzo, S., Traum, D.: Virtual humans for learning. *AI Magazine* **34**(4), 13–30 (2013)
 18. Traum, D., Jones, A., Hays, K., Maio, H., Alexander, O., Artstein, R., Debevec, P., Gainer, A., Georgila, K., Haase, K.: New dimensions in testimony: Digitally preserving a holocaust survivor’s interactive storytelling. In: International Conference on Interactive Digital Storytelling. pp. 269–281. Springer (2015)
 19. Venkatesh, V., Morris, M.G., Davis, G.B., Davis, F.D.: User acceptance of information technology: Toward a unified view. *MIS quarterly* pp. 425–478 (2003)